

AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO TRAINING IN THE FORMATION OF MORAL QUALITIES THROUGH PRIMARY SCHOOL SUBJECTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the purpose and objectives of the integrated approach in education and the organization of the curriculum. Advice is given on planning integrated lessons and the ability to find connections between subjects.*

Key words: *integration, integrated approach, adaptation, information and communication technologies, educational resources.*

Why educate children? One of the main goals of teaching is to teach students to use their knowledge in practice. The ability to see the connection between theoretical knowledge and the outside world. And elementary school is the first step in obtaining knowledge, where they acquire their first knowledge and ideas about the world around them, skills in the interaction of science with nature and society, as well as the ability to solve various practical and life problems. To achieve this goal, we must use an integrated approach to teaching. Also in the history of pedagogy in each period of improvement in education, where special attention was paid to preparing students for independent living. Where students have high mental abilities, but cannot apply them in practice. The solution to these problems can be integration. After all, it is an integrated approach in education in primary school that will help students accept the world as a whole. The solution to these problems using an integrated approach in education has been considered since the time of J. A. Comenius, but the very concept of “Integration” was first introduced in the 11th century by the Englishman G. Spencer. The word integration is translated from Latin integration - connection, restoration. Integration is the process of combining the previously stated into one whole, as well as combining information into one. An integrated approach in education is the establishment of interdisciplinary connections, the combination of several topics, subjects, information, as a single one. Here we can also conclude that integration is the goal of learning, or integration can be considered as a means of learning.

An integrated curriculum allows children to continue learning in a holistic way, without the constraints often imposed by subject boundaries. Early childhood programs focus on the interconnectedness of all learning areas, helping children master the basic learning tools. It recognizes that the primary school curriculum includes reading, writing, speaking, literature, mathematics, science, health, physical education, music, and the visual arts. The curriculum also includes investigative processes and technology. Integrated teaching and learning processes allow children to acquire and use basic skills in all areas of content and develop positive attitudes to continue successful learning in the early grades. Integration recognizes and builds relationships that exist between all things. An integrated curriculum implies learning that is synthesized within traditional subject areas and learning experiences that must be interconnected. This approach develops the child's ability to transfer their learning to other channels. Research also shows that an integrated approach to learning is compatible with the brain. “The brain learns best in real life, multi-path, immersive-style learning...fragmented, fragmented presentation can forever kill the joy and love of learning” (Jensen, 1996). The more connections the brain makes, the more opportunities there are for high-level inferences.

The rationale for the need for integration in the curriculum can be said to be relevant today. Because it is in the integrated learning approach that information and communication technologies are used to transfer information with the appropriate curriculum. Integrating technology into education means using smartphones, tablets, computers and televisions to improve the quality of education for students. There are different methods to use information and communication technologies. For example, for explanation of new material with the help of video, the use of audio materials to improve the quality of oral speech. After all, video and audio materials help not only improve the quality of education, but also increase students' interest in acquiring knowledge. Also, in integrated lessons on the use of ICT, you can teach students how to use them correctly, because new technologies have become a part of our lives, without which it is difficult to imagine a world.

Features of an integrated curriculum and comprehensive program include: experiences to develop children's attitudes, skills and knowledge. And also help them make connections across the curriculum. Activities that provide a wide range of abilities; activities that are initiated and directed by both the teacher and the child; whole class, small group and individual experiences; opportunities for critical and creative thinking; teacher, peer and self-esteem; opportunities to experience learning as a meaningful whole. There are many possible routes towards an integrated approach. There is no one "right way". The comfort level of starting, the length of the journey and the rate of progress of teachers will vary. However, as the curriculum becomes less fragmented, the teacher sees new opportunities for integrated learning and teaching.

Planning an integrated curriculum. The core program promotes learning that is relevant, focused, and rewarding. If we want children to be attracted to experiences, they must be shaped by children's interest and enthusiasm. This means choosing topics, projects or areas of study based on the knowledge that children have, and drawing up a plan based on children's curiosity. This does not mean a non-directional, ever-changing scavenger hunt for answers to the question of the day. Then the children's need for research becomes a means of integration. The teacher's responsibility is to create a plan that will provide the volume and depth needed to provide a valuable educational experience for all children. To provide direction and balance, the teacher needs to make long-term or annual plans that can be reviewed and adjusted throughout the year.

An integrated approach, there is also such a thing as integrated art. Integrated art is defined as an activity that induces in the learner an emotional or kinesthetic state that is in some way analogous to the concept being studied and that results from heightened sensory awareness on the part of the learner. The term "integrated" is used to refer to the integration of artistic experience into the learning process. Integrated experience in the field of arts provides opportunities for the implementation of the following processes: perceptual cognition; metaphorical ways of thinking; use of alternative forms of communication. The main task of teaching art is to develop students' creative abilities in art through independent artistic expression and research, through respect for their spontaneous perception and creativity as the basis for developing students' independence and individuality. The basis of artistic expression is precisely the experience of students, with the help of which students interpret and rethink the visible individual experience of the world around them. Unlike traditional teaching methods, project-based learning provides learning from experience and research, which leads to the integration of content from different areas, as well as a deeper understanding and application of knowledge. Working on a project, students play an active role at all stages of the project and at the same time have the opportunity for comprehensive personal development. Classes link students' emotional, aesthetic and social activities. It is the responsibility of teachers to structure their teaching in such a way that students can develop the appropriate cognitive structure for learning how to study in the visual arts. The atmosphere created by the

teacher should be such that students can spontaneously and freely express their thoughts and feelings, expand their horizons and connect separate areas of knowledge.

Implementation. In many schools, integrated art has been introduced and is widely used to teach subjects that keep students' attention. The justification for the need to integrate the arts into the education system has been discussed by many art teachers and others interested in the completeness of general education. Approaches include having students visit a museum, describe the paintings and tell the background of the painting, and then ask the students to write essays about their visit to the museum. Another example of teaching students through the arts is to have them first read a chapter of a story and then ask them to write a summary of the chapter with a painting. History teaching can also be done through role play where students act out characters in the classroom. Another method that can be used for first grade or younger students to teach about animals can be done by having them hear the sounds of different animals and asking them to recognize them.

The advantages of this method. Integrating the arts in the classroom helps students connect with the world they live in. The underlying principle of the integration of the arts can be summarized as follows: there is a similarity between the arts and other subjects; incorporating art into other subjects helps speed up and facilitate the learning process; art promotes creativity.

The requirement for this type of curriculum is that students who have been trained in the Arts Integration Method have more knowledge and understanding of the relationships between the arts, and have developed an understanding of the arts. It is also argued that integrated art activities will help the child connect their knowledge to the outside world and help them transfer their art knowledge to many other subjects.

An integrated approach, better and longer-term acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes, which are improved through the students' own efforts, research and understanding through an active approach to learning content and practical work. The implementation of the project task inspired the students to stimulate perceptual, volitional and intellectual abilities through the search for connections in various subjects and content; strengthened self-confidence through the acquisition of new knowledge, skills, and through the creation of specific products that will be applicable; this has inspired the development of curiosity and motivation for the successful implementation of tasks through a problem-solving approach to learning and practical work with art materials. Student job satisfaction, intrinsic motivation and creativity are indicators of the adequacy of planned tasks, methods and approaches to learning and teaching, as well as further recommendations when planning future learning activities.

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